

Social Operant Conditioning Standard Protocol – Dougherty Lab

Overview

Humans and other social species find social interaction inherently rewarding. Facets of social motivation are critical to the development and maintenance of healthy social functioning. Autism spectrum Condition (ASC) is defined in part by deficits in social communication and social interaction, yet a long standing hypothesis is that the root deficit may actually be in social motivation (Chevallier et al., 2012). While current behavior assays in mice can answer questions regarding direct social interactions or sociability (i.e., full contact interactions and the social approach task), assays for assessing social motivation (how much work an animal is willing to do for social reward) are not well established. Thus we developed a task to directly examine motivation for social interaction. We modified standard mouse operant conditioning chambers to create an automated system in which social motivation is directly assessed by quantifying nose pokes performed for access to a social partner.

The standard protocol includes:

- ❖ **2 days of habituation:** both experimental and stimulus mice are in their respective areas (operant chamber and stim cage, respectively), the door is set to open the entire habituation trial, and ribbon lights are on red light set to 75-80 lux (Lux meter inside the experimental chamber). This trial lasts 30 min and should be recorded through Noldus Ethovision or Any-Maze for tracking of social interactions.
- ❖ **3-10 days of FR1 (Fixed Ratio 1):** both experimental and stimulus mice are in their respective areas (operant chamber and stim cage, respectively), and one nose poke into the correct hole (aka active hole; counterbalanced between groups) opens the door allowing for a social interaction for 12 sec. The incorrect hole does nothing. The house light is unplugged, the cue light in the hole illuminates during a correct poke and reward, and the house ribbon lights are on red light set to 75-80 lux (Lux meter inside the experimental chamber).
- ❖ **Consistency criteria:** Mice move on to PR3 when they reach consistency criteria for three consecutive days, and are then considered *consistent performers*. The earliest a mouse can reach these criteria is FR1 day 3 and the latest is FR1 day 12; if a mouse reaches criteria for the first time on FR1 day 10, it will be tested on day 11 and then 12 if necessary to see if it continues to reach these criteria. The criteria that must be met for 3 consecutive days are:
 - At least 40 total nose pokes
 - 3:1 ratio correct/incorrect nosepokes
 - At least 75% of rewards include the test mouse entering the interaction zone (interaction attempts).
 - If by day 10, experimental mice do not reach criteria for FR3, they are considered *inconsistent performers* and will move on to PR3 on day 11.
- ❖ **3 days of PR3 (Progressive ratio 3):** both experimental and stimulus mice are in their respective areas (operant chamber and stim cage, respectively), progressively larger amounts of nose pokes into the correct hole (counterbalanced between groups) are required to open the door and allow for interaction for 12 sec. The incorrect hole does nothing. The house light is unplugged, the cue light in the hole illuminates during a correct poke and reward, and the house ribbon lights are on red light set to 75-80 lux (Lux meter inside the experimental chamber).
 - The progressive ratio 3 is: 1, 3, 6, 9, 12, etc. The number of correct nosepokes required to elicit a reward (door opening to a 12 sec interaction) goes up by 3 after every reward.

Section 1: Main Procedure - Supplies, Experiment Set Up, Running the Experiment, Operant cleaning instructions, Checking for interaction criteria

Supplies:

- Autoclaved corn cob bedding with red measuring cup (70-80g)
 - It is important to use clean bedding for each animal! Autoclaved corn cob bedding can be acquired from DCM. Will need at least three bags for a cohort of 40 mice.
- 70% Ethanol Spray
- 0.02% chlorhexidine solution (Nolvasan) spray
- Paper towels
- 20 stimulus chambers (2 for each operant box)
- 30 white matte acrylic (1) flooring and (2) wall pieces
- Compressed air can for cleaning Arduino cases
- Operant apparatuses inside sound-attenuating boxes, all power supply, cables, cameras, computer, etc.; see full list for set up below.
- Noldus license dongle #2 (No. 8382)
- Paint can opener and/or large binder clips
- Ladder or step stool

Experimental Set Up:

1. Operant Chamber Set up:

Habituation: The animal does not get access to the holes during habituation. Tape over the holes, and then turn them upside down in their panels – place the rectangular metal half wall piece on top (see Fig HAB HOLES).

FR1 Training & PR3 Testing: The animal needs to access to the holes during FR1 training and PR3 testing. Remove tape from the holes, and then turn them right side up in their panels – place the rectangular metal half wall piece on top (see Fig CHAMBER).

1. Clean the operant chambers with 70% EtOH fully (see **Operant Cleaning Instructions** section).
2. Clean white acrylic insert with EtOH and add to bottom of apparatus.
3. Clean the top piece of clear acrylic and the two side pieces of white matte acrylic (matte side faces inward).
4. Clean the white box the stimulus chamber sets on with 70% EtOH and the Stimulus chambers with chlorhexidine.
 - a. This is adhered to the floor with Velcro and has Velcro and push pins to hold the stim chamber in place.
5. Place 1 red cup of clean corn cob bedding in the operant chamber tray – shake horizontally to equally distribute the bedding
6. Turn on the ribbon lighting to red at 75-80 lux
 - a. Use the Lux meter to confirm setting with lux meter inside experimental chamber.
7. Confirm the CCTV camera is centered in the box and aligned appropriately on the top of the test chamber.
 - a. If the cameras get hazy, unscrew the lens and gently clean the front, back and inside of the lens and camera with a microfiber glass cloth.
8. Turn on cameras by powering on the large metal power strip (Cameras 1) and the smaller black power strip (Cameras 2) and the three quad processors (Cameras 3).

2. Noldus Ethovision Setup:

1. Use the Basler Pylon software to adjust the camera (4-1-2020: Suz could not get this feature to work with the quad processors)
 - i. Open Pylon viewer. Click on the Basler acA1300 camera. Click Open camera on top left. Click single shot to view a snap shot of view. Click on Continuous shot for live feed. If this looks good, proceed to Noldus.
 1. Adjustments can be made in this program to adjust contrast, etc for the camera view. (See manual in Box\JDLAB\Behavior\Behavior Assay Procedures and Protocols\T-maze folder)
2. Open up the Ethovision template file from here the desktop (use 032023 SoOp2 [as of 4-137-23]). Open the most recent version (as defined by the folder name)
 - a. Save as your study name, e.g. 020420_Social_Operant.exvt.
 - b. To create a new file from a template, select New Experiment > New from template:

- c. Select Use a custom template:

- d. Browse for your previous experiment or template the desktop (use 032023 SoOp2 [as of 4-137-23]) Open the most recent version, as defined by the folder name):

- e. Name it your study ID:

3. The Follow Steps (4-6) should be set up already if using the template. However, double check that they are indeed set up correctly for your study.
4. Under Experiment Settings, make sure that your file is being saved to a location on the local C drive. Copy your experiment to the box at the end of each testing day.
 - a. Select Live tracking with 3 sources. The Euresys Pico Alert board sn/4040 – VID1, 2 and 3 should show up. Resolution: 640x480, Frame Rate 29,97 (NTSC). Click on the camera icon to pull up the camera field of view.
 - i. Within the Quad processor, under Camera Settings, Brightness = 0 and Contrast = 0
 - ii. In the image tab, Brightness = 0, Contrast = 1849, and Saturation = 0
 - b. Number of Areas = 10 (equal to the number of apparatuses used), Number of Subjects per Arena = 2, Tracked Features = Center-point, nose-point, tail-base detection.
5. In Arena Settings, create an arena for every chamber. Include a full apparatus area, a Test chamber, a stim chamber, and a Exp and Stim interaction zone.
 - a. Draw the arena to ONLY include the exp and stim chamber, so the door area and any cords, etc are excluded. The tracking only happens within the arena, so eliminating anything that tracking could jump to by creating a specific arena will reduce aberrant tracking.
 - b. Calibration: Use a KNOWN distance in the chamber so you can see it in Arena settings and use it for your calibration measure.
 - c. **IMPORTANT – move your labels off of the chamber so that you can see the entire chamber clearly. Drag the arrows to the zone it labels.**
 - d. The social interaction zone for the experimental animals should measure should measure 5.92 cm wide and 8 cm long. Make sure it starts just the right of the door (the door should not be in the zone).

- e. The stimulus interaction zone should measure 5.92 cm wide and 8 cm long. Make sure it starts just the left of the door (the door should not be in the zone).
- f. Make sure the stimm and Exp zones line up, i.e. are at the same spot on the Y axis.

a.

- 6. In Trial Control Settings, create the following: Use 3601 seconds because tracking will begin 1 sec before the MED-V testing.

- 7. Under Detection Settings, select Automated Set up and follow the procedure. Select Unmarked Subjects.
 - a. As of 4-17-23: Use the “Red light detection settings” in template.
 - b. You have to have an animal in every arena (test and stim chambers) you are trying to optimize.
 - c. **IMPORTANT – Use extra mice with the same coat color to optimize lighting and tracking so habituation is not disrupted.**
- 8. Under Trial List, set up your trials/run order.
- 9. Include a user-defined column with “Role”: Exp or Stim.

System		System		System		System		User-defined		User-defined		User-defined	
Acquisition status	Arena settings	Trial Control settings	Detection settings	ID	DAY	Role							
The current status of acquisition per arena	The arena settings used for acquisition	The trial control settings used for acquisition	The detection settings used for acquisition	Text	Text	Text							
	Arena	Trial	Trial	Subject	Trial	Subject							
	Trial	Subject	No.										
Acquisition (38 acquired)	Apparatus 3	Subject 1	1	Acquired			7.1						Exp
		Subject 2	2	Acquired			3.1_stim						Stim
	Apparatus 4	Subject 1	3	Acquired			2.1						Exp
		Subject 2	4	Acquired			5.1_stim						Stim
	Apparatus 5	Subject 1	5	Acquired			1.2						Exp
		Subject 2	6	Acquired			3.2_stim						Stim
	Apparatus 6	Subject 1	7	Acquired			3.2						Exp
		Subject 2	8	Acquired	Social Operant Chambers	30 min tracking	5.2_stim			Habituation Day 2			Stim
	Apparatus 7	Subject 1	9	Acquired			6.4						Exp
		Subject 2	10	Acquired			3.3_stim						Stim
	Apparatus 8	Subject 1	11	Acquired			4.3						Exp
		Subject 2	12	Acquired			5.3_stim						Stim
	Apparatus 9	Subject 1	13	Acquired			5.1						Exp
		Subject 2	14	Acquired			5.1						Exp

3. **Optional ANY-maze Setup:**

Any-maze should be set up 3604 seconds – this allows you to start the tracking for both mice (stim then test mouse) first before starting the med-associates program.

- Can use the 102519 Any-maze operant protocol as a template.
- ANY-maze camera settings:

4. **Create a Run Order:**

- Prior to the day of testing, a run order should be created.
- See example sheets: on server here: [Box/jdlab/Behavior/Behavior Assay Procedures and Protocols/Social Operant Protocol Folder/Example Run Order Sheet - Use as Template.xlsx](#)).
- Print 2 copies of the run order and this protocol for reference during test.
 - One run order will be taped to the wall above the stim chambers, and the other will remain on a clip board by the test animals and to note consistent performers.
 - Print each day on a separate page. (Highlight text, Page Layout, Set Print Area)
- 021119 data suggests that the task does not work with only 2 mice in the cage for males (have not tested this with females). **Make sure all cages have at least 3 mice.**

Our data suggest that mice perform best in this assay in the afternoon. **Therefore, ideal times for testing are between 12pm – 6pm (if on 6am/6pm on/off light schedule).**

Counterbalancing run order: For counterbalancing, it is important that each experimental group and controls are represented evenly across cages and across runs. For your first run, make sure that the groups are represented evenly and are distributed across the cages. For example, Run 1: Cage 1 = WT, Cage 2 = mutant, Cage 3 = WT, Cage 4 = mutant, Cage 5 = WT, Cage 6 = mutant, Cage 7 = WT, and Cage 8 = mutant. Then, alternate the experimental group in each cage for each run. For example, cage 1 run order: Run 1 = WT, Run 2 = mutant, Run 3 = WT, Run 4 = mutant. Your run order may become more complex with the addition of more genotypes/experimental groups and between each sex. Apply the same counterbalancing techniques.

- Each experimental mouse should be paired with a NOVEL stim mouse (sex- and age-matched) each day – this includes habituation, FR1, FR3, and PR.
- Need to have at least one stim mouse per experimental mouse. Near the end of the experiment, you may start to recycle the pairings because you'll run out of mice.
- You need at least one stimulus mouse per experimental mouse, as stimulus mice can't be used more than once per day of testing. Need at least 10 stim mice of each sex, ideal to have 15 or more regardless of the number of experimental mice.

Running the Experiment:

Test animals should be brought into testing room (B54B) 30 min to 1 hour prior to testing to acclimate to the testing environment.

- Stim mice should be kept separate from Test mice (for example, stim mice on cart and test mice on the counter). Further the female test mice should be kept separate from the male test mice (for example, on opposite end so the counter).
- Take the lids off of all cage before starting.

The testing room and those adjacent should remain quiet.

1. *At the start of each test day:*

1. MARK THE TAILS OF THE MICE

- a. Mark stim mice on one day and test mice on the other – alternating each day.
- b. Mark the cages in at least 3 different colors (red, blue and green are suggested). This will help keep track of what animal goes in which cage because each run will require mice from multiple cages.

2. TURN ON THE EQUIPMENT:

- a. **Turn on Arduinos:** Press the power button on the USB hub into which all the Arduinos are plugged. The doors should open and close. *it is very important that the arduinos are turned on before the med associates power box; failure to follow this order will result in the doors opening randomly during testing.
- b. **Turn on Med Associates Power box:** Press the green power button. This will power all the boxes. The fans turn on and the arduinos stopped their cycle in with the doors in the closed position.
- c. **Turn on cameras:** Power on the large metal power strip (Cameras 1) and the smaller black power strip (Cameras 2) and the three quad processors (Cameras 3).

3. TEST THE DOOR IN EACH BOX TO MAKE SURE IT WORKS EVERY DAY.

a. To Test the doors:

- i. Ensure operant system and USB hub are turned on
- ii. Open MED-PC on computer
- iii. Click “Load” button; in the Load window, check all boxes, ensure Program is “SocialFR1” (leave other columns blank), then click “Apply” and then “OK”
- iv. Click the “Send” button; in the Send window, check all boxes and click “OK”
- v. All operant boxes should now be functional; test by sticking a finger in the correct nosepoke hole of each
- vi. When finished testing, click the “Stop” button; in the Stop window, select “Stop, discard data”, check all boxes, and click “OK”

Habituation:

There are two 30 min habituation trials on two consecutive days. Both the experimental and stimulus mice are placed in the apparatus. The house light is on the whole time to indicate the trial is running, the cue light in the hole illuminates during a correct poke and reward, and the house ribbon lights are on red light at 75-80 lux. The trial is tracked via Ethovision/Any-maze. The door remains open for the entire habituation trial.

Testing:

Testing is 60 min. Both the experimental and stimulus mice are placed in the apparatus. The house light is on the whole time to indicate the trial is running, the cue light in the hole illuminates during a correct poke and reward, and the house ribbon lights are on red light at 75-80 lux. The trial is tracked via Ethovision/Any-maze.

2. Work flow:

1. Make sure the boxes are clean with fresh bedding before starting.
 - a. Use red measuring cup.
2. Open **MED-PC software** (MED-PC V).
3. Set Once: Click on **Data>File Options**.
 - a. Format for data files: “Annotated” make sure is selected
 - b. File naming conventions: “Create a new file for every session, named according to date, time and subject” make sure is selected.
 - c. Data directory: locate your folder on the local drive for saving your data.
 - i. Always save to the local drive and transfer your files to the server EVERY DAY at the end of testing.
 - ii. NO spaces in the folder names – this will muck up the scripts.
 - d. Automatic data backup frequency: “10”
4. **Load program:** In MED-PC software (MED-PC V), click “**Load Box**” Icon or click Control-O; in the Load window,
 - a. check all boxes that will be used,
 - b. Under **Procedure**, select the desired program (see below)
 - i. MED-PC_V_Social_FR1-L: **FR1** left hole is correct, 1 nose pokes to elicit reward
 - ii. MED-PC_V_Social_FR1-R: **FR1** right hole is correct, 1 nose pokes to elicit reward
 - iii. MED-PC_V_Social_PR-L: **PR3** left hole is correct, progressive ratio by 3 of nose pokes to elicit reward
 - iv. MED-PC_V_Social_PR-R: **PR3** right hole is correct, progressive ratio by 3 of nose pokes to elicit reward
 - c. Under **Subject**, enter subject ID (e.g. “1.1”) and the test version “_FR1/FR3/PR” (e.g. 1.1_FR1)
 - d. Under **Experiment**, enter the cohort study NUMBER (e.g. 091719)
 - e. Under **Group**, enter the number for the test day, not including habituation, only test days, (i.e. 1 – 10).
 - i. So, group should only be a number.
 - f. Under **Comment**, enter the Test version, i.e. FR1, FR3, PR.
 - g. Click **APPLY**.
5. Click the **Send icon (traffic signal)**.
 - a. Signal: select *Start*
 - b. Boxes: select the boxes that you wish to start.
 - c. STOP HERE AND LOAD MICE.
6. Place the stim mice in the stim chambers in the boxes:

- a. There are two stimulus chambers per box. Use a clean one for each trial, and clean out the previously used chamber during the next trial with chlorhexidine (see **Operant Cleaning Instructions** section). Let dry the remainder of the trial.
 - b. If you are using Ethovision for tracking, you must load all the mice at once for a trial, you cannot start tracking for a single mouse at a time, which is possible with ANY-maze. (4-11-2020)
 - i. **Put all the stimulus mice in the stim chambers in the boxes BEFORE putting any experimental mice in the operant chambers.**
 - ii. **Remove all of the experimental mice BEFORE removing the stim mice – the experimental mice should NEVER be in the chambers without the stimulus mice in the stim chambers.**
 - c. When using any-maze, can start male boxes first and then start females second.
7. Then place the experimental mice in the chambers and close the doors.
 8. Start tracking software (BEFORE starting Med-PC program):
 - a. If using Ethovision – start the Ethovision tracking (*Tracking duration should be 3601 for Ethovision.*)
 - b. If using Any-maze, start the stim mouse tracking first and then immediately start the experimental test mouse tracking. (*Tracking duration should be 3602 for Any-maze*)
 9. Immediately after starting the tracking, start the testing in Med-PC V software:
 - a. Click **ISSUE**.
 - b. Then click **Close**.
 - i. The test is now running. The red box light also turns on.
 10. **If using Any-maze:** Repeat steps 9-12 for the female stim and female experimental mice.
 11. Option: TO STOP A TEST BEFORE ITS COMPLETION: click the Stop Box icon (red hexagon with X).

12. At the end of each trial:
 - a. Remove the experimental mice first.
 - i. The experimental mice should never be in the boxes without the stimulus mice
 - b. Remove the stimulus mice second.
 - i. If running with **any-maze** and females are still testing, start to clean the males' cages.
 - c. Using 70% EtOH, wipe down the inside of the operant chamber (all metal parts and acrylic floor). Make sure to get all urine and feces, as well as the cage bars for the door.
 - i. See **Operant Cleaning Instructions** section.

- d. Dispose of the dirty bedding (trash can), and clean the tray with 70% EtOH.
 - e. Add one new cup of clean bedding to tray and replace.
13. Set up computer for next trial (steps 7-8 above).
14. Run next trial, steps 9-13 above.

*****The Med-PC V data is saved to a .txt file. That is all of the med associates data, it is NOT saved in an experiment file anywhere that can be retrieved again.**

*****Back up Ethovision file and all .txt files at the end of each test day into a BackUp folder on the Box in your study folder.**

Once mice reach criteria, do PR and drop out, skip the apparatus in the trial list in Ethovision. Do not try to track an empty chamber.

Operant cleaning instructions:

Before starting a study:

1. Give the operant chambers a deep clean with 70% EtOH – taking everything a part, and cleaning each part (acrylic, metal grid, bottom, sides, bars, doors and frame, white box, metal tray) with EtOH.
2. Clean each stimulus chamber well with chlorhexidine.
3. Remove the door frame and clean under all metal walls with EtOH
4. Wipe out the operant sound attenuating boxes with EtOH paper towel.
5. Sweep and mop the room. Make sure there are no stuck feces on the floor – scrub up and stuck poo.
6. Clean the counter surfaces of the room with EtOH.

In between runs:

1. Pick up feces and soak up urine puddles with paper towel.
2. Dump out bedding in trash.
3. Spray the tray with 70% EtOH, both inside and outside, and wipe clean. Refill with bedding.
4. Spray inside of operant chamber with EtOH only (do not use nolvasan). Using the large alligator clip or paint can opener, pull up the white acrylic sheet, and spray and wipe the bottom of the sheet and the metal grid. Spray and wipe underneath the chamber where the tray goes. Wipe down the bars, both sides, the door, and inside the holes.
7. Spray & wipe the white box with EtOH.
8. Stimulus chambers: dump out any urine and feces into the trash can. Remove top from chamber and spray both top and bottom liberally with chlorhexidine. Clean immediately, do not let the chlorhexidine dry. Let air out until next run.
 - a. This can be done on the back counter in between the male and female experimental cages.

Once a week while running (or more frequently if needed)

1. Sweep and mop the room. Make sure there are no stuck feces on the floor – scrub up and stuck poo.
2. Clean the counter surfaces of the room with EtOH.

Following the end of the study:

1. Give the operant chambers a deep clean with 70% EtOH – taking everything a part, and cleaning each part (acrylic, metal grid, bottom, sides, bars, doors and frame, white box, metal tray) with EtOH.
2. Clean each stimulus chamber well with chlorhexidine.
3. Remove the door frame and clean under all metal walls with EtOH
4. Wipe out the operant sound attenuating boxes with EtOH paper towel.
5. Sweep and mop the room. Make sure there are no stuck feces on the floor – scrub up and stuck poo.
6. Clean the counter surfaces of the room with EtOH.

It is the responsibility of the experimenter to conduct the full cleaning at the end of the study – help can be coordinated but this cleaning needs to happen within two weeks of the end of the study.

We do not want the room to smell like urine. Please make sure to keep all metal clean with 70% EtOH, and the floor and counter swept and cleaned with EtOH (counter) or mopped with Swiffer/Lysol spray.

Checking for interaction criteria:

All SPSS scripts and Java Programs for data reduction can be found here:

Box\JDLAB\Behavior\Behavior Assay Procedures and Protocols\Social Operant Protocol Folder\Scripts for reducing data

NEVER edit original SPSS scripts. Save a copy into your experiment folder and adjust file names, etc in that one.

How to check for criterion: 75% of rewards the Exp mouse ATTEMPTED to interact with the stim by entering the interaction zone (change on 12-1-22):

This is done for all animals that reach the first two criteria (40 total nose pokes and 3:1 ratio correct:incorrect). This can be done for multiple animals at once (you do NOT have to do each animal individually).

These steps line up the Med Associates reward timing with the Ethovision tracking data to determine if the experimental mouse was in the interaction zone during rewards.

1. **Med Associates Reward Data:** Combine all .txt files for FR1 trials.
 - a. Copy all the FR1 txt files into one folder. Copy the CombineTextFiles_v1.1.jar into that folder too.
 - b. Open the "CombineTextFiles_v1.1.jar" tool, select the files you want to combine (*hence usefulness of copying all FR1 txt files to one folder*).
 - i. A .csv file will be saved in the folder above where the files are located under the name of the folder in which the txt files are located.
 - ii. May need to do this twice because the Combine tool cannot handle more than 170-ish files at once. The tool will add to a file if one already exists with the name of the folder.
 1. If you run the tool more than once, it will add a new header at the top of the new, additional data. Delete any extra header rows with in the data.
 - c. Open the .csv file, rename the sheet 'DATA', and save as an .xlsx file.
 - d. Open the SPSS syntax file: "**Data Organization for MedAss txt Data to Total Values and Rewards by Time_3-19-23.sps**".
2. Follow the commented instructions and run this syntax.
 - a. This syntax will also save a file of the total daily values of the data. You can ignore this file if you have no use for it.
3. This Syntax will save the Reward Data into the correct format for the InteractionScore tool steps below. Specifically, it will reorganize the data and save an excel file that looks like this with each second of the hour test as a column and a 1 indicating a reward was occurring and a 0 indicating no reward was occurring:

TEST_TYPE																
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	
	TEST_TYPE	ID	Cohort	Day	s1	s2	s3	s4	s5	s6	s7	s8	s9	s10	s11	s12
2	FR1	Test2	30820	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
3	FR1	Test3	30820	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	FR1	Test2	30820	3	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	FR1	Test3	30820	3	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
6																
7																

4. **Ethovision Data for social interaction zone time (1 sec bins):** Export frequency in the Stimm and Exp interaction zones in 1 sec bins from Ethovision.
 - a. **Need to have the Ethovision license dongle to enable all modules while reducing these data.**
 - b. Interpolate criterion: if missing samples (can output into data file) is less than <7%, do not interpolate.
 - c. Interpolate all missing data for trials ran. Go to track editor and select your first trial that you are checking criteria for. Check that both the first sample and last sample of each track have a tracked point for each apparatus. Then click on the Auto Select... button. Then click on the interpolate button (cross shape) and select "missing samples" and in the drop down select "All arenas" to interpolate and fill in all missing data within the trial. Repeat for all trials you are checking. (6-10-21)

The image shows two windows from the Ethovision software. The top window is 'Sample List' with a dropdown menu set to 'Apparatus 6'. It contains a table with columns for Time, EXP (Center X, Y, Area), and STIM (Center X, Y, Area). The bottom window is 'Track Editor' showing 'Trial 15' and a toolbar with an 'Auto Select...' button. A dialog box titled 'Auto Select Samples' is open, showing options for 'Missing samples', 'Sample distance', 'Surface area', and 'Nose-tailbase length'. The 'Scope' section is set to 'All arenas' and 'All subjects'. A blue arrow points from the 'Auto Select...' button in the Track Editor to the 'Auto Select Samples' dialog box.

Time	EXP			STIM		
	Center X (cm)	Center Y (cm)	Area (cm ²)	Center X (cm)	Center Y (cm)	Area (cm ²)
00:00:00.000	71.949	56.771	9.03	-	-	-
00:00:00.033	71.949	56.873	9.03	-	-	-
00:00:00.067	71.949	57.076	9.03	-	-	-
00:00:00.100	71.924	56.975	9.03	-	-	-
00:00:00.133	71.949	56.949	9.03	-	-	-
00:00:00.167	72.000	56.898	9.03	-	-	-

- d. Under Trial List, create a new user-defined variable in Ethovision for mouse **Role** – Exp or Stim:

The image shows the 'Trial List' window in Ethovision. It features a table with columns for Trial, Arena, Subject, No., and several System and User-defined columns. A red box highlights the 'User-defined' column for 'Role', which contains values like 'Exp' and 'Stim'.

Trial	Arena	Subject	No.	System	System	System	System	User-defined	User-defined	User-defined
Trial 4	Apparatus 3	Subject 1	1	Acquired				7.1		Exp
		Subject 2	2	Acquired				3.1_stim		Stim
	Apparatus 4	Subject 1	3	Acquired				2.1		Exp
		Subject 2	4	Acquired				5.1_stim		Stim
Apparatus 5	Subject 1	5	Acquired				1.2		Exp	
		6	Acquired				3.2_stim		Stim	
	Subject 2	7	Acquired		Social Operant Chambers	30 min tracking		6.4	Habituation Day 2	Exp
Apparatus 6	Subject 1	8	Acquired					5.2_stim		Stim
		9	Acquired					6.4		Exp

e. Set up the Ethovision Analysis>Data Profile like this:

- i. This example is for one day in one box/apparatus for one trial. It is easiest if you only pull down the day/box/trial you are working with to make it easier.
- ii. Select settings under the 1 sec bin (Result) and indicate the time bin, and select results per zone for **each Exp and then Stimm** respectively.

- iii.
- f. Create an **Analysis Profile** EACH for time in the Exp zone (this is the social interaction zone in the experimental side) and for the Stimm zone (this is the social interaction zone in the stimulus side).

- i.
- ii. Select Frequency under Trial Statistics
- g. Under Results>Statistics & Charts, select your data profile and analysis profile, then adjust the layout to look like this:

- i.
- h. Select Calculate, and your data should look like this:

						In zone	
						Stimm / Center-point	
						Frequency	
						Subject 1	Subject 2
0:00:00-0:00:01	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:01-0:00:02	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:02-0:00:03	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:03-0:00:04	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:04-0:00:05	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:05-0:00:06	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:06-0:00:07	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:07-0:00:08	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:08-0:00:09	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:09-0:00:10	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-
0:00:10-0:00:11	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	-

- i.
- i. Select Export Data.
 - i. For missing data, leave the box blank so nothing is in the cells.
 - ii. Repeat for both Stimm and Exp zones.
- j. Combine exported Stimm & Exp Zone files:
 - i. Open each file in excel (that matches for day/trial) and change the headers to these (creating macros in Excel make this much more efficient if you have many files):

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Trial	Apparatus 3	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Exp.1	Exp.2	
							In zone	In zone	
							Exp / Cent	Exp / Center-point	
							Frequency	Frequency	
							Subject 1	Subject 2	
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:	7.1	Exp	In Exp	1	
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:	7.1	Exp	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:	7.1	Exp	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:	7.1	Exp	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:	7.1	Exp	In Exp		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:05-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp		

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Trial	Apparatus 1	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Stim.1	Stim.2	
							In zone	In zone	
							Stimm / Ce	Stimm / Center-poin	
							Frequency	Frequency	
							Subject 1	Subject 2	
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:00-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm		
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:00-0:	7.1	Exp	In Stimm		
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:01-0:	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm		
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:01-0:	7.1	Exp	In Stimm		

- iii. Then, WITHOUT sorting the data in any way, copy over columns H-I from the Stim file to the Exp file, like this:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
	Trial	Apparatus 3	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Exp.1	Exp.2	Stim.1	Stim.2
								In zone	In zone	In zone	In zone
								Exp / Cent	Exp / Cent	Stimm / Ce	Stimm / Ce
								Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency
								Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp		1			
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:05-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:05-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					

- iv.
- v. Convert the Trial and Apparatus columns to numeric columns by deleting all string text. Easiest way to do this is to select those two columns from row 2 down and find and replace "Trial " with nothing and "Apparatus " with nothing.
 - 1. There are spaces after Trial and Apparatus. Make sure you add those in to your find – replace.
- vi. Delete any habituation days. Those can be added to a separate file.
- vii. Then delete rows 2-5 in the combined file so it looks like this:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	Trial	Apparatus	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Exp.1	Exp.2	Stim.1	Stim.2
2	7	3	1	0:00:00-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
3	7	3	1	0:00:00-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp		1			
4	7	3	1	0:00:01-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
5	7	3	1	0:00:01-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
6	7	3	1	0:00:02-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
7	7	3	1	0:00:02-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
8	7	3	1	0:00:03-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
9	7	3	1	0:00:03-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					

- viii.
- k. Name the Sheet "DATA" and then save as an excel file.
- l. Repeat for all Trials/Apparatuses, if you are doing these separately (although all trials can be done at once).
- m. Run through the code in this syntax file: **Data Organization for Ethovision 1 sec bins 6-13-21.sps**.
 - i. It will organize the file so it looks like this:

Time	ID	Day	Ex	STIM
1	Test2	1	0	0
2	Test2	1	0	0
3	Test2	1	0	0
4	Test2	1	0	0
5	Test2	1	0	0
6	Test2	1	0	0
7	Test2	1	0	0
8	Test2	1	0	0
9	Test2	1	0	0
10	Test2	1	0	0
11	Test2	1	0	0
12	Test2	1	0	0
13	Test2	1	0	0
14	Test2	1	0	0
15	Test2	1	0	0
16	Test2	1	0	0
17	Test2	1	0	0
18	Test2	1	0	1
19	Test2	1	0	0
20	Test2	1	0	0
21	Test2	1	0	0

- ii.
- iii. The syntax will also export the data as an excel file.
- n. Open the excel file and save as a .csv file.
 - i. I do not export from SPSS into a .csv file because it does not open correctly.

5. Use the InteractionScore_v3.1 to extract the social interaction data during reward times.
 - a. Open your previously exported med associates FR1 file
 “*_MedAssociates_Reward_Data_FR1.xlsx” and save as a .csv file.
 - b. Copy the InteractionScore_v3.1 to the folder with the .csv files.
 - 1) double click on the **InteractionScore_v3.1.jar**. Then it will open a file system to ask for input data files. It only accepts CSV format, so you'll have to convert excel to CSV.
 - 2) firstly, it will ask for a MedAssociates file.
 - 3) then, it will ask for a NoldusInteraction file.
 - 4) at last, it will ask for the path of the output folder.
 - 5) waiting for the program to finish. It should only take about 10 seconds.

In the output folder you specified earlier, you will get a CSV file which contains subjects interaction scores. And you will also get a log file, which reports the process and invalid/suspicious data from the input.
 - c. The data is spit out into I, S, E and B data for each reward. We need to add these 4 columns for each DAY for each Subject, which we will do in step e below.
 - d. Name the sheet ‘DATA” and Save the .csv file as an excel file: “*_FR1_PercentDaily_Interaction_Data_longform.xlsx”
 - e. Use the **Social_Operant_Interaction_Percent_Daily_ATTEMPTS_Syntax_12-1-22.sps** syntax file to determine how many times the experimental animal entered the interaction zone during a reward. This syntax will determine the number of NON-zero cells in the “E” and “I” columns (experimental only and interaction columns), then divide that by the total cells in the column.
6. Visually determine if you mouse hit more than 75% attempts to meet criterion for moving on.

Section 2: Data Reduction: Total daily values, Reward timing with interactions

There are three major steps outlined below to reduce all the necessary data.

Step A, Total daily values: reduces total daily values of both med associates and Ethovision tracking data.

Step B, Reward timing with interactions: reduces interaction data (social zone occupation during rewards) from med associates and Ethovision tracking data.

Step C, Percent daily interactions & Attempts: reduces percent interaction data (rewards during which both animals are in the interaction zones) and interaction attempts by the experimental mouse (rewards during which the experimental mouse was in the interaction zone regardless of the location of the stimulus mouse) from med associates and Ethovision tracking data.

The following variables should be included in one dataset for analysis:

Total_Rewards – collected from the **A** data reduction step.

Total_Nosepokes– collected from the **A** data reduction step.

Correct_Nosepokes– collected from the **A** data reduction step.

Incorrect_Nosepokes– collected from the **A** data reduction step.

Percent_Correct– collected from the **A** data reduction step.

Percent_Incorrect– collected from the **A** data reduction step.

Breakpoint– collected from the **A** data reduction step.

Total_Distance_Traveled – collected from the Ethovision tracking data in **A** data reduction step.

Entries_into_Interaction_Zone– collected from the Ethovision tracking data in **A** data reduction step.

Duration_in_Interaction_Zone– collected from the Ethovision tracking data in **A** data reduction step.

Interaction_Time – collected from the **B** data reduction step below

Stim_Only_Reward_Time – collected from the **B** data reduction step below

Exp_Only_Reward_Time – collected from the **B** data reduction step below

Empty_Reward_Time – collected from the **B** data reduction step below

Percent_Daily_Interactions – collected from the **C** data reduction step below.

Percent_Daily_Attempts - collected from the **C** data reduction step below.

No_Interactions – collected from the **C** data reduction step below.

Daily_Interactions – collected from the **C** data reduction step below.

No_Attempts – collected from the **C** data reduction step below.

Daily_Attempts – collected from the **C** data reduction step below.

Here's a template for how the final Social Operant Data spreadsheet should look:

Box/jdlab/Behavior/Behavior Assay Procedures and Protocols/Social Operant Protocol Folder/SocialOperant_Data_Template_9-3-20.sav

- 3-19-23: Let's update this after this next operant run.

All SPSS scripts and Java Programs for data reduction can be found here:

Box\JDLAB\Behavior\Behavior Assay Procedures and Protocols\Social Operant Protocol Folder\Scripts for reducing data

NEVER edit original SPSS scripts. Save a copy into your experiment folder and adjust file names, etc in that one.

Before reducing the Ethovision data:, create heatmaps to ensure all of your zones are correctly placed.

To do this, create a data profile for the Test chamber and for the Stim chamber.

1. Under Analysis > Data Profiles, create a data profile for all TEST days (exclude habituation) for the mouse in the Exp Zone.
 - a. Under Filter, select DAY and then select only the Test days.
 - b. Under Nesting, select In zone, select Test. Should look like this:

2. Under Analysis > Data Profiles, create a data profile for all TEST days (exclude habituation) for the mouse in the Stim Zone.
 - c. Under Filter, select DAY and then select only the Test days.
 - d. Under Nesting, select In zone, select Stim. Should look like this:

3. Under Analysis> Results, select Heatmap Visualization. On the top, select either your Exp or Stim data profile.
 - e. Under Heatmap settings, Colors: select Over heatmaps, Smoothing = 7; Show/Hide tab: select both subjects, Merging method: Mean, Custom layout with no Columns or rows.
 - f. Click on the Show/Hide tab on the upper left corner, and select Arena Features. Select the Test, Stim, Exp, and Stimm zones to overlay the zones on the heatmaps.
 - g. Click Plot Heatmaps. Will look like this:

4. Adjust any of your zones under Arena Settings if they do not appear to be correctly placed. For example, the heatmap above shows that the chamber with the X needs to have the stim chamber adjusted – the boundaries are not over the actual chamber.

Step A: How to reduce the total daily values into a dataset:

NEVER edit original SPSS scripts. Save a copy into your experiment folder and adjust file names, etc in that one.

1. **Med Associates Reward Data: FR1 trials (PR3 files will be done later).**
 - a. Copy all the FR1 txt files into one folder. Copy the CombineTextFiles_v1.1.jar into that folder too.
 - b. Open the “CombineTextFiles_v1.1.jar” tool, select the files you want to combine (*hence usefulness of copying all FR1 txt files to one folder*).
 - i. A .csv file will be saved in the folder above where the files are located under the name of the folder in which the txt files are located.
 - ii. May need to do this twice because the Combine tool cannot handle more than 170-ish files at once. The tool will add to a file if one already exists with the name of the folder.
 1. If you run the tool more than once, it will add a new header at the top of the new, additional data. Delete any extra header rows with in the data.
 - c. Open the .csv file, rename the sheet ‘DATA’, and save as an .xlsx file.
 - d. Open the SPSS syntax file: **“Data Organization for MedAss txt Data to Total Values and Rewards by Time_3-19-23.sps”**.
 - e. Follow the commented instructions and run this syntax. It will accomplish the steps below in gray:
 - i. Rename Column Headers:
 1. Create a Coded_ID and Protocol\$ column: In your excel file, use the Text to Column function under Data tab to split the File_1 column at the underscore.
 - a. Insert a new column to the right of the ‘File_1’ column.
 - b. Highlight the ‘File_1’ column. Select Data tab, Text to Columns, Delimited, Other (insert an underscore, _). Then okay.
 - c. Relabel the ‘File’ column ‘Coded_ID’.
 - d. Label new “1” column ‘Protocol\$’.
 - i. delete the .txt from each cell using Find-Replace ‘.txt’ with nothing.
 2. Relabel ‘Group’ → ‘Day’
 3. Create a ‘Side\$’ column: Use the Text to Column under Data tab to split the ‘MSN’ column at the dash and then rename the column Side\$ (then delete the ‘MSN’ column).
 - a. Insert a new column to the right of the ‘MSN’ column.
 - b. Highlight the ‘MSN’ column. Select Data tab, Text to Columns, Delimited, Other (insert 1 dash, -). Then okay.
 - c. Delete the ‘MSN’ column.
 - d. Label new column ‘Side\$’.
 4. Relabel ‘F’ = Total_Rewards’
 5. Relabel ‘B_0’ = ‘Total_Nosepokes’
 6. Relabel ‘B_1’ = ‘Correct_Nosepokes’

- 7. Relabel 'B_2' = 'Incorrect_Nosepokes'
- 8. Relabel 'B_3' = 'Percent_Correct'
- 9. Relabel 'B_4' = 'Percent_Incorrect'
- ii. Delete Columns:
 - 10. E, G-A_9, B_5 through the end.
- b. This Syntax will also save the Reward Data into the correct format for the InteractionScore tool steps below. Specifically, it will reorganize the data and save an excel file that looks like this with each second of the hour test as a column and a 1 indicating a reward was occurring and a 0 indicating no reward was occurring:

TEST_TYPE	ID	Cohort	Day	s1	s2	s3	s4	s5	s6	s7	s8	s9	s10	s11	s12
FR1	Test2	30820	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
FR1	Test3	30820	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
FR1	Test2	30820	3	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
FR1	Test3	30820	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

- i. The file for InteractionScore tool will be names
 - “*_MedAssociates_Reward_Data_FR1.sav”
 - ii. The file with all daily values will be named “*_Social_Operant.sav”
2. For PR3 trials, need to combine files and then run through SPSS script, as outlined below.
- a. It may be useful to copy all the PR txt files into one folder prior to step b.
 - b. Open the “CombineTextFiles_v1.1.jar” tool, select the files you want to combine (all PR files across all test days; hence usefulness of copying all PR txt files to one folder).
 - i. A .csv file will be saved in the folder above where the files are located under the name of the folder in which the txt files are located.
 - c. Open the .csv file, rename the sheet 'DATA', and save as an .xlsx file.
 - d. Open the SPSS syntax file: “Data Organization for MedAss txt PR Data to Total Values and Rewards by Time_12-1-22.sps”.
 - e. Follow the commented instructions and run this syntax. It will accomplish the steps below in gray:
 - i. Rename Column Headers:
 - 1. Create a Coded_ID and Protocol\$ column: In your excel file, use the Text to Column function under Data tab to split the File_1 column at the underscore.
 - a. Insert a new column to the right of the 'File_1' column.
 - b. Highlight the 'File_1' column. Select Data tab, Text to Columns, Delimited, Other (insert an underscore, _). Then okay.
 - c. Relabel the 'File' column 'Coded_ID'.
 - d. Label new “1” column 'Protocol\$'.
 - i. delete the .txt from each cell using Find-Replace 'txt' with nothing.
 - 2. Relabel 'Group' → 'Day'

3. Create a 'Side\$' column: Use the Text to Column under Data tab to split the 'MSN' column at the dash and then rename the column Side\$ (then delete the 'MSN' column).
 - a. Insert a new column to the right of the 'MSN' column.
 - b. Highlight the 'MSN' column. Select Data tab, Text to Columns, Delimited, Other (insert 1 dash, -). Then okay.
 - c. Delete the 'MSN' column.
 - d. Label new column 'Side\$'.
4. Relabel or create new variables for Total_Rewards, Total_Nosepokes, Correct_Nosepokes, Incorrect_Nosepokes, Percent_Correct, Percent_Incorrect, Breakpoint.
 - a. A = Correct_Nosepokes
 - b. B = Incorrect_Nosepokes
 - c. C = Total_Rewards
 - d. X = PR (breakpoint)
5. Delete Columns rest of columns.
- f. The Syntax then saves this as daily values and combines with the FR1 daily values for one files named "*_Social_Operant.sav"
- g. 12-1-22: The "h" step below should change to match the reward data formatting for the InteractionScore tool as for the FR1 since the PR .txt files now have a D-array. The instructions will be modified once we confirm this protocol works and is a permanent change.
- h. This Syntax will also save the Reward Data into the correct format for the InteractionScore tool steps below (however you will need to paste in the actual reward data, this is just the starting template). Specifically, it will reorganize the data and save an excel file that looks like this with the latency for each reward column labeled ready for pasting in of data from .txt files.
 - i. The file for InteractionScore tool will be named "*_MedAssociates_Reward_Data_PR.sav"
 - ii. An excel file will be exported named "*_MedAssociates_Reward_Data_PR.xlsx".
 1. Open excel file, find and replace all "#NULL!" with nothing/an empty cell.
 - iii. Open each PR .txt file through excel import wizard (excel> open> select the .txt files), select Delimited, Delimiters Other "."
 - iv. For each file, copy in the G array 0 – N as rewards R1 – RN. Paste special > Transpose:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1	TEST_TYPEID	Cohort	Day	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	
2	PR	6.1	20420	7									
3	PR	4.3	20420	8									
4	PR	5.3	20420	8									
5	PR	7.3	20420	8									
6	PR	1.3	20420	10									
7	PR	1.1	20420	10									
8	PR	3.3	20420	10									
9	PR	1.2	20420	11									
10	PR	2.1	20420	11									
11	PR	3.2	20420	11									
12	PR	4.3	20420	11									
13	PR	6.4	20420	11									
14	PR	6.5	20420	11									
15	PR	7.1	20420	11									
16	PR	4.2	20420	11									
17	PR	5.2	20420	11									
18	PR	6.3	20420	11									
19	PR	7.2	20420	11									
20	PR	2.2	20420	11									
21	PR	4.1	20420	11									
22	PR	2.3	20420	13									
23	PR	5.1	20420	13									
24	PR	6.2	20420	14	190.15	581.3	874.8	1465.2	1849.1	2944.1			
25													
26													

v.

3. **Ethovision Outcome Variables:** Distance traveled, total time and entries into interaction zones for each the test mouse and the stimulus mouse.
 - a. **Need to have the Ethovision license dongle to enable all modules while reducing these data.**
 - b. Interpolate all missing data for trials ran. Go to track editor and select your first trial that you are checking criteria for. Check that both the first sample and last sample of each track have a tracked point for each apparatus. Then click on the Auto Select... button. Then click on the interpolate button (cross shape) and select “missing samples” and in the drop down select “All arenas” to interpolate and fill in all missing data within the trial. Repeat for all trials you are checking. (6-10-21)

- c. Under Trial List, create a new user-defined variable in Ethovision for mouse **Role** – Exp or Stim:

- d. Create a data analysis profile for each the Exp Total Values and the Stim Total Values. Filter the results for only the Test or Stim zones respectively.

i.

- e. Create an Analysis Profile Distance traveled, time and entries into the social interaction zone for each experimental and stim mouse respectively:

ii.

- f. Then, calculate the data under Results > Statistics & Charts. Organize the layout like this:

- iii.
- g. Then select the appropriate profiles and select Calculate. Your data should look like this:

				Distance moved		In zone				
				Center-point		Exp / Center-point				
				Total		Frequency		Cumulative Duration		
				Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	
Trial 4	Apparatus 3	Habituation Day 2	3.1_stim	Stim		1381.5399		15		93.0597
			7.1	Exp	3347.2285		115		358.2916	
	Apparatus 4	Habituation Day 2	2.1	Exp	4552.4514		72		346.7801	
			5.1_stim	Stim		-		-		-
	Apparatus 5	Habituation Day 2	1.2	Exp	4536.8936		93		404.7381	
			3.2_stim	Stim		-		-		-
	Apparatus 6	Habituation Day 2	3.2	Exp	-		0		0.0000	
			5.2_stim	Stim		4058.1870		107		298.0981
	Apparatus 7	Habituation Day 2	3.3_stim	Stim		-		-		-
			6.4	Exp	4786.9619		273		745.4454	
Apparatus 8	Habituation Day 2	4.3	Exp	5960.0268		279		527.0604		
		5.3_stim	Stim		-		-		-	
Apparatus 9	Habituation Day 2	3.4_stim	Stim		-		-		-	
		5.1	Exp	4858.3930		107		361.7284		
Apparatus 10	Habituation Day 2	2.5_stim	Stim		-		-		-	
		6.5	Exp	5244.9117		139		375.9426		
Trial 5	Apparatus 3	Habituation Day 2	1.1_stim	Stim		-		-		-
			6.1	Exp	4585.8049		122		730.1969	
	Apparatus 4	Habituation Day 2	3.1	Exp	399.0027		10		45.7124	
			5.4_stim	Stim		4111.9530		81		687.2539
	Apparatus 5	Habituation Day 2	1.2_stim	Stim		3938.1713		78		1038.4718
			7.2	Exp	-	-		-		-
	Apparatus 6	Habituation Day 2	4.1_stim	Stim		964.3365		22		32.1989
			4.2	Exp	1600.6874		60		79.1792	
	Apparatus 7	Habituation Day 2	1.3	Exp	1082.3931		40		100.0000	
			1.3_stim	Stim		3651.7171		184		484.4178
Apparatus 8	Habituation Day 2	2.3	Exp	-		-		-		
		4.2_stim	Stim		4751.4207		148		431.4982	

- iv.
- h. A separate sheet will be exported for the experimental mouse and for the stimulus mouse.
- v. Missing value Representation: use a blank cell. Do not merge column headers.

i. Open each file in excel and change the headers to these:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
Trial	Apparatus	Day	ID	Role	Test_Distance.1	Test_Distance.2	Exp_Zone_Entries.1	Exp_Zone_Entries.2	Exp_Zone_Time.1	Exp_Zone_Time.2
					Distance moved	Distance moved	In zone	In zone	In zone	In zone
					Center-point	Center-point	Exp / Center-point	Exp / Center-point	Exp / Center-point	Exp / Center-point
					Total	Total	Frequency	Frequency	Cumulative Duration	Cumulative Duration
					Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2
7	Apparatus 3	1	2.1_stim	Stim		498.734			11	77.978
7	Apparatus 3	1	7.1	Exp	9387.73		210		835.302	
7	Apparatus 4	1	2.1	Exp	3674.62		147		534.401	
7	Apparatus 4	1	4.2_stim	Stim		6674.57		161		832.166
7	Apparatus 5	1	1.2	Exp	6723.7		212		467.401	
7	Apparatus 5	1	2.2_stim	Stim		3997.94		114		418.919
7	Apparatus 6	1	3.2	Exp	3849.22		171		435.936	
7	Apparatus 6	1	4.3_stim	Stim		1532.98		65		91.1578
7	Apparatus 7	1	2.3_stim	Stim		6098.78		215		1055.69
7	Apparatus 7	1	6.4	Exp	3615.91			114		423.924
7	Apparatus 8	1	4.3	Exp	5816.14			231		496.797

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
Trial	Apparatus	Day	ID	Role	Stim_Distance.1	Stim_Distance.2	Stim_Zone_Entries.1	Stim_Zone_Entries.2	Stim_Zone_Time.1	Stim_Zone_Time.2
					Distance moved	Distance moved	In zone	In zone	In zone	In zone
					Center-point	Center-point	Stimm / Center-point	Stimm / Center-point	Stimm / Center-point	Stimm / Center-point
					Total	Total	Frequency	Frequency	Cumulative Duration	Cumulative Duration
					Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2
4	Apparatus 3	Habituation Day 2	3.1_stim	Stim		2593.82			42	798.532
4	Apparatus 3	Habituation Day 2	7.1	Exp	957.156		11		210.11	
4	Apparatus 4	Habituation Day 2	2.1	Exp						
4	Apparatus 4	Habituation Day 2	5.1_stim	Stim		3233.09		87		1414.55
4	Apparatus 5	Habituation Day 2	1.2	Exp						
4	Apparatus 5	Habituation Day 2	3.2_stim	Stim		3031.23		45		1616.75
4	Apparatus 6	Habituation Day 2	3.2	Exp	3223.94		75		989.022	
4	Apparatus 6	Habituation Day 2	5.2_stim	Stim		74.7423		4		6.20621
4	Apparatus 7	Habituation Day 2	3.3_stim	Stim		2733.05		64		1324.52
4	Apparatus 7	Habituation Day 2	6.4	Exp						

j. Then, WITHOUT sorting the data in any way, copy over columns F-K from the Stim file to the Exp file, like this (but make sure there is a "role" column, accidentally forgot to grab a pic w/ it):

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
Trial	Apparatus	Day	ID	Test_Distance.1	Test_Distance.2	Exp_Zone_Entries.1	Exp_Zone_Entries.2	Exp_Zone_Time.1	Exp_Zone_Time.2	Stim_Distance.1	Stim_Distance.2	Stim_Zone_Entries.1	Stim_Zone_Entries.2	Stim_Zone_Time.1
				Distance moved	Distance moved	In zone	In zone	In zone	In zone	Distance moved	Distance moved	In zone	In zone	In zone
				Center-point	Center-point	Exp / Center-point	Exp / Center-point	Exp / Center-point	Exp / Center-point	Center-point	Center-point	Stimm / Center-point	Stimm / Center-point	Stimm / Center-point
				Total	Total	Frequency	Frequency	Cumulative Duration	Cumulative Duration	Total	Total	Frequency	Frequency	Cumulative Duration
				Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1
4	Apparatus 3	Habituation 3.1_stim			1381.54		15		93.0597	2593.82		42		
4	Apparatus 3	Habituation 7.1		3347.23		115		358.292		957.156		11		210.11
4	Apparatus 4	Habituation 2.1		4552.45		72		346.78						
4	Apparatus 4	Habituation 5.1_stim								3233.09		87		
4	Apparatus 5	Habituation 1.2		4536.89		93		404.738						
4	Apparatus 5	Habituation 3.2_stim								3031.23		45		
4	Apparatus 6	Habituation 3.2				0		0		3223.94		75		989.022
4	Apparatus 6	Habituation 5.2_stim			4058.19		107		298.098		74.7423		4	
4	Apparatus 7	Habituation 3.3_stim								2733.05				64
4	Apparatus 7	Habituation 6.4		4786.96		273		745.445						
4	Apparatus 8	Habituation 4.3		5960.03		279		527.06		11.4398		3		0.533868
4	Apparatus 8	Habituation 5.3_stim									2993.04			91
4	Apparatus 9	Habituation 3.4_stim									3131.39			72
4	Apparatus 9	Habituation 5.4		4858.30		107		361.738						

m. Then delete rows 2-5 in the combined file so it looks like this:

Trial	Apparatus	Day	ID	Role	Test_Distance.1	Test_Distance.2	Exp_Zone_Entries.1	Exp_Zone_Entries.2	Exp_Zone_Time.1	Exp_Zone_Time.2	Stim_Distance.1	Stim_Distance.2	Stim_Zone_Entries.1	Stim_Zone_Entries.2	Stim_Zone_Time.1
7	3	1	2.1_stim	Stim		498.734			11	77.978					263
7	3	1	7.1	Exp	9387.73		210		835.302		342.073		6		
7	4	1	2.1	Exp	3674.62		147		534.401		5784.8		189		
7	4	1	4.2_stim	Stim		6674.57		161		832.166		2617.58			82
7	5	1	1.2	Exp	6723.7		212		467.401		2945.72		95		
7	5	1	2.2_stim	Stim		3997.94		114		418.919		3974.54			131
7	6	1	3.2	Exp	3849.22		171		435.936		1796.42		57		
7	6	1	4.3_stim	Stim		1532.98		65		91.1578		4185.63			130

n. Convert the Trial and Apparatus columns to numeric columns by deleting all string text. Easiest way to do this is to select those two columns from row 2 down and find and replace "Trial " with nothing and "Apparatus " with nothing.

vi. There are spaces after Trial and Apparatus. Make sure you add those in to your find – replace.

vii. Delete any habituation days. Those can be added to a separate file.

p. Name the Sheet "DATA" and then save as an excel file.

q. Run through the code in this syntax file: **Data Organization for Ethovision Distance and Zone Values 6-11-21.sps.**

viii. It will combine and rearrange your file so it is ready for analysis.

Step B: How to combine reward timing from Med Associates with Interaction data from Ethovision:

Step 1: Reorganize the Ethovision entries/frequency data in 1 sec bins Export frequency in the Stimm and Exp interaction zones in 1 sec bins from Ethovision.

1. Need to have the Ethovision license dongle to enable all modules while reducing these data.

- a. Interpolate all missing data for trials ran. Go to track editor and select your first trial that you are checking criteria for. Check that both the first sample and last sample of each track have a tracked point for each apparatus. Then click on the Auto Select... button. Then click on the interpolate button (cross shape) and select “missing samples” and in the drop down select “All arenas” to interpolate and fill in all missing data within the trial. Repeat for all trials you are checking. (6-10-21)

- b. Under Trial List, create a new user-defined variable in Ethovision for mouse **Role** – Exp or Stim:

2. Set up the Ethovision Analysis>Data Profile like this:

- a. This example is for one day in one box/apparatus for one trial. It is easiest if you only pull down the day/box/trial you are working with to make it easier.
- b. Select settings under the 1 sec bin (Result) and indicate the time bin, and select results per zone for each Exp and then Stimm respectively.

3. Create an Analysis Profile EACH for time in the Exp zone (this is the social interaction zone in the experimental side) and for the Stimm zone (this is the social interaction zone in the stimulus side).

a. Select Frequency under Trial Statistics

4. Under Results>Statistics & Charts, select your data profile and analysis profile, then adjust the layout to look like this:

5. Select Calculate, and your data should look like this:

						In zone	
						Stimm / Center-point	
						Frequency	
						Subject 1	Subject 2
0:00:00-0:00:01	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:01-0:00:02	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:02-0:00:03	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:03-0:00:04	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:04-0:00:05	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:05-0:00:06	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:06-0:00:07	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:07-0:00:08	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:08-0:00:09	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:09-0:00:10	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	
0:00:10-0:00:11	2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm				-
	7.1	Exp	In Stimm			-	

6. Select Export Data.
 - a. For missing data, leave the box blank so nothing is in the cells.
 - b. Repeat for both Stimm and Exp zones.
7. Combine exported Stimm & Exp Zone files:
 - a. Open each file in excel (that matches for day/trial) and change the headers to these (creating macros in Excel make this much more efficient if you have many files):

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Trial	Apparatus 3	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Exp.1	Exp.2	
							In zone	In zone	
							Exp / Cent	Exp / Center-point	
							Frequency	Frequency	
							Subject 1	Subject 2	
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp	1		
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp			
Trial	7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:05-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp			

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
Trial	Apparatus 1	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Stim.1	Stim.2	
							In zone	In zone	
							Stimm / Ce	Stimm / Center-poin	
							Frequency	Frequency	
							Subject 1	Subject 2	
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:00-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm			
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:00-0:(7.1	Exp	In Stimm			
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:01-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Stimm			
Trial	7	Apparatus 1	1	0:00:01-0:(7.1	Exp	In Stimm			

- b. Then, WITHOUT sorting the data in any way, copy over columns H-I from the Stim file to the Exp file, like this:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
	Trial	Apparatus 3	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Exp.1	Exp.2	Stim.1	Stim.2
								In zone	In zone	In zone	In zone
								Exp / Cent	Exp / Cent	Stimm / Ce	Stimm / Ce
								Frequency	Frequency	Frequency	Frequency
								Subject 1	Subject 2	Subject 1	Subject 2
1	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
2	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:00-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp		1			
3	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
4	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:01-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
5	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
6	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:02-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
7	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
8	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:03-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
9	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
10	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:04-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
11	Trial 7	Apparatus 3	1	0:00:05-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					

- c. Convert the Trial and Apparatus columns to numeric columns by deleting all string text. Easiest way to do this is to select those two columns from row 2 down and find and replace "Trial " with nothing and "Apparatus " with nothing.
 - i. There are spaces after Trial and Apparatus. Make sure you add those in to your find – replace.
- d. Delete any habituation days. Those can be added to a separate file.
- e. Then delete rows 2-5 in the combined file so it looks like this:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	Trial	Apparatus	Day	Time_Bin	ID	Role	Zone	Exp.1	Exp.2	Stim.1	Stim.2
2	7	3	1	0:00:00-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
3	7	3	1	0:00:00-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp		1			
4	7	3	1	0:00:01-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
5	7	3	1	0:00:01-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					
6	7	3	1	0:00:02-0:(2.1_stim	Stim	In Exp					
7	7	3	1	0:00:02-0:(7.1	Exp	In Exp					

- 8. Name the Sheet "DATA" and then save as an excel file.
- 9. Repeat for all Trials/Apparatuses.
- 10. Run through the code in this syntax file: **Data Organization for Ethovision 1 sec bins 6-13-21.sps**.
 - i. It will organize the file so it looks like this:

Time	ID	Day	Ex	STIM
1	Test2		1	0
2	Test2		1	0
3	Test2		1	0
4	Test2		1	0
5	Test2		1	0
6	Test2		1	0
7	Test2		1	0
8	Test2		1	0
9	Test2		1	0
10	Test2		1	0
11	Test2		1	0
12	Test2		1	0
13	Test2		1	0
14	Test2		1	0
15	Test2		1	0
16	Test2		1	0
17	Test2		1	0
18	Test2		1	0
19	Test2		1	0
20	Test2		1	0
21	Test2		1	0

- b. The syntax will also export the data as an excel file.
- 11. Open the excel file and save as a .csv file.
 - a. I do not export from SPSS into a .csv file because it does not open correctly.

Step 2: Combining social interaction data from entries and reward data:

- Any data collected **after** March 2020, use the InteractionScore_v3.1 for FR1 data. **12-1-22: use the InteractionScore_v3.1 for PR data too, we've added a D-array. The protocol will be permanently revised once we confirm this procedural change.**

FR1 data:

1. Open your previously exported med associates FR1 file “*_MedAssociates_Reward_Data_FR1.xlsx” and save as a .csv file.
2. Copy the InteractionScore_v3.1 to the folder with the .csv files.
 - 1) double click on the **InteractionScore_v3.1.jar**. Then it will open a file system to ask for input data files. It only accepts CSV format, so you'll have to convert excel to CSV.
 - 2) firstly, it will ask for a MedAssociates file.
 - 3) then, it will ask for a NoldusInteraction file.
 - 4) at last, it will ask for the path of the output folder.
 - 5) waiting for the program to finish. It should only take about 10 seconds.

In the output folder you specified earlier, you will get a CSV file which contains subjects interaction scores. And you will also get a log file, which reports the process and invalid/suspicious data from the input.
3. The data is spit out into I, S, E and B data for each reward. We need to add these 4 columns for each DAY for each Subject, which will happen in steps below.
4. Name the sheet ‘DATA’ and Save the .csv file as an excel file:
 - “*_FR1_Interaction_Data_longform.xlsx”
 - a. Also save a copy as “*_FR1_PercentDaily_Interaction_Data_longform.xlsx”
 - a. This will be used in **Step C** below.
5. For the final data set, sum the total I, S, E and B columns for each animal for each day so that there is one row of data for each animal for each day.
 - a. To do this, use this SPSS syntax:)12-1-22) **use Social_Operant_Interaction_Sum_Syntax_12-1-22**
 - b. For note purposes only:
 - i. I = Interaction_Time
 - ii. E = Exp_Only_Reward_Time
 - iii. S = Stim_Only_Reward_Time
 - iv. B = Empty_Reward_Time

PR data:

6. Open your previously exported med associates PR file “*_MedAssociates_Reward_Data_PR.xlsx” and save as a .csv file.
 - a. Also save a copy as “*_PR_PercentDaily_Interaction_Data_longform.xlsx”
 - i. This will be used in **Step C** below.

- b. Make sure the med associates file does not have decimal places. To change this, highlight the data, and click the move decimal button until all values after the decimal place are gone.

- c.
7. Copy the InteractionScore_v3.1.jar to the folder with the .csv files.
- 1) double click on the **InteractionScore_v3.1.jar** Then it will open a file system to ask for input data files. It only accepts CSV format, so you'll have to convert excel to CSV.
 - 2) firstly, it will ask for a MedAssociates file.
 - 3) then, it will ask for a NoldusInteraction file.
 - 4) at last, it will ask for the path of the output folder.
 - 5) waiting for the program to finish. It should only take about 10 seconds.

In the output folder you specified earlier, you will get a CSV file which contains subjects interaction scores. And you will also get a log file, which reports the process and invalid/suspicious data from the input.

NOTE: the format required for the different InteractionScore versions can be checked in their respective folder here: Box\JD LAB\Behavior\Behavior Assay Procedures and Protocols\Social Operant Protocol Folder\Scripts for reducing data There is an example .cvs file for each time and rewards.

8. The data is spit out into I, S, E and B data for each reward. We need to add these 4 columns for each DAY for each Subject, which occurs below.
9. Name the sheet 'DATA' and Save the .csv file as an excel file: "*_PR_Interaction_Data_longform.xlsx"
10. For the final data set, sum the total I, S, E and B columns for each animal for each day so that there is one row of data for each animal for each day.
 - a. To do this, use this SPSS syntax: **Social_Operant_Interaction_Sum_Syntax_PR_12-1-22.sps**.
 - i. This syntax will also combine the FR1 Interaction Summed data with the PR data into one dataset.

Step C: Percent daily interactions & Attempts:

1. Name the sheet 'DATA' and Save the .csv file as an excel file: **"*_FR1_PercentDaily_Interaction_Data_longform.xlsx"**
2. Use the **Social_Operant_FR1_Percent_Daily_Outcomes_Syntax_3-19-23.sps** syntax to add up daily total and percent interactions and interaction attempts.
3. Name the sheet 'DATA' and Save the .csv file as an excel file: **"*_PR_PercentDaily_Interaction_Data_longform.xlsx"**
4. Use **Social_Operant_PR_Percent_Daily_Outcomes_Syntax_3-19-23.sps** syntax to add up daily total and percent interactions and interaction attempts and combine PR and FR1 data.

These files need to be combined into your full dataset:

(* = indicates your unique study identifier)

1. ***_Social_Operant.sav** = total outcome variables by day for the med associates data (total rewards, total nose pokes, correct nose pokes, incorrect nose pokes, percent correct, percent incorrect, breakpoint).
 - a. Add all other datasets to this one.
2. ***_Ethovision_Data.sav** = total tracking data outcomes by day (for both Exp and Stim, distance traveled, entries into and time in social interaction zone)
3. ***_InteractionScoreSum.sav** = total interaction data for each day (Empty_Reward_Time, Exp_Only_Reward_Time, Interaction_Time, Stim_Only_Reward_Time)
4. ***_InteractionScore_DailyPercent_Full.sav** = daily interaction values per rewards (Rewards, No_Interactions, Daily_Interactions, Percent_Daily_Interactions)

Best way to combine is to copy in the variables from 2-4 into 1, making sure the datasets are sorted in the same manner and that the IDs and Days line up correctly.

For data analysis, see this google sheet:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bLFDIBKdHthIYUwoKlae_w8e2C4ov7_hcrsfK3otICA/edit?usp=sharing

Section 3: Full Equipment Set Up:

***This task requires 4 full days of set up with testing set up with extra mice. Plan accordingly.

Med-Associates:

- Sound attenuating cubicle (ENV-022MD)
- Modular Test Chamber (ENV-307X-CT)
 - SmartControl Panel,
 - Illuminated nosepokes (x2)
 - Head entry detector
 - House cue light
- 28 VDC to TTL adapter (SG-231)
- Interface Cabinet with Decode (#DIG-700G)
- SmartControl Interface Module (#DIG-7166)

Computer and Power:

- PCI card (DIG-704PCI-2)
- Computer with necessary capabilities (recommended from Med Associates)

Arduino:

- Arduino Uno REV3 [Arduino Uno Rev3 — Arduino Online Shop](#)
- USB power hub (Amazon.com: SABRENT 60W 10-Port USB 3.0 Hub Includes 3 Smart Charging Ports with Individual Power Switches and LEDs + 60W 12V/5A Power Adapter (HB-B7C3) : Everything Else)

Camera:

- BNC cameras (Amazon.com : Vanxse CCTV Mini Spy Pinhole Security Camera Hd 1.8mm 120degree CCD 1000tvl Hidden Mini CCTV Surveillance Camera : Electronics)
- BNC extension cables (optional) (BNC Video Power Cable 100 ft, Black Premade BNC Video Power Cable/Wire for Security Camera, CCTV, DVR, Surveillance System, Plug & Play: Amazon.com: Industrial & Scientific)
- Power source cables for cameras (Amazon.com : R-Tech12V 1A Switching Power Supply Power Adapter 5 Pack - Black, UL-Listed, Power Cord with 5.5x2.1mm Tips, AC 100-240V to DC 12V 1A Transformers for LED Strip Lights, CCTV Camera, Routers, Home Appliances : Power Converters : Electronics)
- 3 Quad Processors (Amazon.com: Podofu HD Color Video Quad Splitter CCTV Video Camera Processor System Kit Switcher Metal Case with 6 BNC Adapter).

Lighting:

- LED strip lighting (customizable to desired length) Commercial Electric 8 ft. LED RGB Under Cabinet Light DT8800-8F (homedepot.com).
- PVC foam weather strip M-D Building Products 1/2 in. x 10 ft. Gray High-Density PVC Foam Weatherstrip Tape 02311 (homedepot.com)

Door/Motor:

- Metal bar grate with 6mm bar spacing (DIMENSIONS)
- Door (CAD included) *recommend printing in white filament, if using video tracking.

- Door frame (CAD included)
- Eyelet PVC block (½" x ½")
- Eyelet screw (any size)
- Motor ([Longrunner 10 x MG996R Metal Gear Torque Digital Servo Motor for RC Model Car Boat Helicopter LKY62 : Toys & Games \(amazon.com\)](#))
- Lazer Sharp SlbIBKXL-7 Barrel Swivel with Interlock Snap, Size 7 ([Lazer Sharp SlbIBKXL-7 Barrel Swivel with Interlock Snap, Size 7 - Walmart.com](#))
- filament wire (South Bend Monofilament 10-Pound Test Universal filament wire; [South Bend Monofilament 10-Pound Test Universal filament wire, 650 Yds. - Walmart.com](#))
- Motor stand block (CAD included)

Experimental and Stimulus Chamber:

- Stim chambers 3 7/16" x 6 5/16" (Clear Amac Boxes | The Container Store), cut opening 5.5x8.7cm in lid.
- Square box/base for base stim chamber
- White matte acrylic floor 18x21cm
- White matte acrylic walls 18x21cm
- ½ galvanized steal wire mesh ([GARDEN CRAFT 10-ft x 2-ft Gray Steel Hardware Cloth Rolled Fencing with Mesh Size 1/2-in x 1/2-in in the Rolled Fencing department at Lowes.com](#))

APPARATUS/EQUIPMENT SETUP

MED-PC-V Script Set up:

To create new/update scripts for Med-PC V:

1. Create the code in a .txt file.
2. Open the Trans software - run as administrator.
3. Create a new file. Paste in your txt from the txt file.
4. Select Translate – Make (As needed). This will create the .mpc file that the Med-PC V needs to run.
5. If no errors, then build the code – select Translate – Build
6. If that is processes successfully, under the Med-PC V software, click on settings > Edit Procedure List and move to the right box the new scripts.

MED Associates Apparatus:

Setup Med Associates operant boxes and install software using the instructions provided by Med Associates.

Lighting Installation:

To reduce glare on the experimental chamber we used self-adhesive weather stripping to create a ledge 4cm from the top of the sound attenuated cubicle. Then place the strip lighting on top of the weather stripping facing upward.

Camera Installation:

The camera can be adhered to the top of the cubicle using a command strip. Take care to ensure camera placement allows for a field of view including both experimental and stimulus chambers. Connect to power and BNC connection not computer. Feed cables through opening in cubicle.

Cameras

All boxes should be equipped with a CCTV board camera mounted from the top facing down into the box. Illumination in each box should be consistent and measured with the Lux meter.

RCA cords travel from the camera in the operant box to a gray quad processor, and the 12V power plugs into the long power strip to power each camera. The yellow connections are the video feed, the red connections are power (do not need white, that is for auditory feed). Each quad processor is then itself connected to a 12V power supply (in back of quad) and the yellow connection of an RCA cord plugs into the PCI card in the back of the computer.

- Make sure the camera is centered and aligned appropriately on the top of the box.

Door Installation:

The Med Associates chamber is modular, meaning the steel wall pieces come in various sizes and can be moved around to facilitate different setups. The most important setup of modular pieces is the door area. You will want to the door area in the middle panel of the right hand wall. Using the smallest modular panels, you need to sandwich the steel bars piece (Fig. DOORa). To avoid the door getting stuck, place the vertical bars on the inside of the operant chamber.

To keep the door in the channel we 3d printed a panel to be taped on between the experimental chamber and the stimulus chamber. You will want to install this panel so the bottom of the opening is in line with the stimulus chamber, when the door is closed the bottom of the door should be below this opening in the panel. (Fig. DOORc)

Motor Installation:

Use the 3D printed motor block using a command strip, then adhere the motor block to the input panel (See Fig MOTOR). The pink motor label needs to be on the right or facing the back seen in MOTOR figure. Cut a long piece of filament wire and attach one end to a barrel swivel snap. Attach that snap to the propeller included with the motor and attach to motor.

Using a command strip attach PVC block with eyelet screw at the top cubicle directly above the where the door will be. Feed the unattached end of filament line through the eyelet. Carefully determine the length of wire needed to allow door to open and close The arm should be at 4pm when the door is open and it moves clockwise to shut the door. (See Fig. DOORb) You can do this by turning on the motor and measuring the length of line used for the movement. Once complete attach a barrel swivel clip and attach to door (test once more to make sure the door opens and closes completely). IMPORTANT: make sure the door is long enough that, when close, it is below the outer door frame so the stimulus mouse cannot gain access to it. If they can, they will try to push the door up.

Arduino Setup:

Use a USB cable to connect the Arduino to a computer that has the Arduino IDE installed (Info about installing the Arduino IDE: www.arduino.cc/en/Guide/ArduinoUno). Upload the social operant code onto the Arduino via the Arduino IDE.

Notes: The cable coming from the TTL box has spots for two wires; one side is black, the other is white. The “ground” wire goes on the black side. The motor has three wires, arranged as follows:

The Arduino can be adhered to the input panel next to the motor (Fig. MOTOR).

The Arduino needs to be plugged into the black med associates TTL adapter box on the left back side of the chamber using a BNC adapter. Then, from the input plug on the TLL adapter box, plug the other end into output 3 on input panel.

To test doors prior to testing each day: Turn on the USB hub to power the Arduinos, leave the Med Associates system off. Without input from the Med Associates system the Arduinos will continue to send a signal to the motors causing the doors to go up and down.

Stimulus Chamber Setup:

The opening of the stimulus chamber was cut using a Dremel. The opening was covered using ½ wire mesh and held in place with glue (Figure STIM BOX). The stimulus chamber needs to be flush with the door opening in the operant chamber and a consistent height. Our lab used 96 slot 1.5 mL tube boxes (cardboard). We found it made the perfect inexpensive base for out stimulus chambers. For cleaning purposes, we wrapped the cardboard box in clear packing tape. Adhere the box to the base of the cubicle using command strips. Use Velcro to keep the stimulus chamber in place on the box. This setup is not required. It is important to have a base that is sturdy and the correct size.

Figure STIM BOX

Experimental Chamber Setup:

To increase video tracking accuracy, we added a matte white acrylic floor and walls to the experimental chamber. The floor sits (matte side up) on top of the metal bar floor installed in the operant box. The walls are applied with tape to the outside of the clear Plexiglas wall of the chamber, to block cored or other objects from interfering with tracking (Figure CHAMBERa)

Figure CHAMBER

Figure MOTOR

Figure DOORa

Figure DOORb

Figure DOORc

Input Panel set up (Figure INPUT PANELS):

- The left nose poke hole (hole closest to the BACK of the box) connects to input 1 (black, white and red wires) and output 1 (orange and green wires) of the input panel.
- The right nose poke hole (hole closest to the door of the box) connects to input 2 (black, white and red wires) and output 2 (orange and green wires) of the input panel.
- Output 3 is the Arduino through the TTL box.

- Output 4 is the house cue light in the operant box (See fig LIGHT).

Figure INPUT PANEL

Figure FULL CHAMBER